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THE IMPORTANCE FROM THE MANAGEMENT SCHOOL IN ADAPTATION TO THE CHANGES

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ABSTRACT

The lack of effective school management can compromise the quality of education and the training of the students, affecting the reputation from the school before the society. The aim of the study is to highlight the importance of school management in the capacity of schools to adapt to social and technological changes, as well as highlight the need of adopt systems of management more efficient to to meet to the demands educational from the society contemporary. The study he was driven through of one bibliographic review, with the analysis of scientific studies, articles and books on the importance of school management in adapting to current changes. The strategy of search considered relevant databases and key terms related to management school, social and technological changes. The results highlight the need urgent need to adopt more efficient management systems to meet demands educational institutions of contemporary society. Furthermore, they emphasize the importance of school management aligned with the needs of the educational environment, seeking strategies that promote the comprehensive education of students. The bibliographic review reinforces the importance crucial from the management school in the capacity of the schools of if adapt to the changes both social as technological. Therefore, the active participation of managers, self-knowledge, understanding of the group that are part of your team and their collaboration in creating standards and actions they are elements essential to the success from the management school in this context.

Keywords: Management school – Social changes – Technological changes –Integral Training

INTRODUCTION

At the moment, to the schools they are facing the pressure of the changes technological and social, and which forces them to renew themselves to meet the needs of students and society. In this context, school management plays a role very important, being responsible for the organization and operation of one school what he has the need of adopt systems of management each time more efficient to meet the educational demands of contemporary society (De Almeida; Of the Saints; Magellan, 2019).

School management needs to be able to adapt to both social and economic changes. as technological. AND essential what the education and your actors recognize the the connection between those concepts, following to the changes node behavior and node process of learning of the students (Guimarães Junior and al., 2022). In that context, school management needs to be aligned with the demands of society, looking for ways to meet these student needs. It is worrying that many schools still face difficulties in adapting to changes and implement systems of management more efficient, the what represents at the moment one of the main challenges. There was one change of paradigm, in what the management school it went out simply from an administrative issue to a transformation process educational and social. Therefore, and disturbing to perceive what they exist schools what yet no adopted systems of management more effective, one time what the lack of effectiveness he can compromising the quality of teaching and the training of students, affecting the society the reputation from the own school.

According to mentioned previously, the management school plays one paper crucial in the capacity of schools to promote a link between education and transformations in students' behavior and learning process. In however, lots of schools to if adapt and implement systems of management efficient, face challenges that are currently one of the main obstacles. There is a clear urgent need to adopt more effective management systems for meet the demands of society, since the lack of effective management ends up compromising the quality of teaching.

To Roller and Hanoff (2021), the attention from the management school he must to be directed to to the needs from the society, searching strategies to supply to the demands educational and promote the complete education of students. The authors leave Of course

this is a fundamental aspect in the educational context and would be however, it is a mistake to attribute less importance to this issue. Thus, it is understood that the management school aligned with to the needs and demands of environment educational, under that optics, win particular relevance and it is done necessary the search put strategies what promote the training integral of the students.

According to highlighted put Of Almeida, Of the Saints, Magellan (2019) and Guimaraes Junior Et Al. (2022), it can be said that school management plays a crucial role in the ability of schools to adapt to social changes and technological. In this context, it is clear that the need to adopt systems of more efficient management to meet educational demands is a reality. The more worrying, however, and to note what the lack of one management school effective he can compromise the quality of teaching and affect the reputation from the school before the society. It is no exaggeration to say that it is important for school management to be aligned with to the needs and demands of environment educational, as highlighted by Roldão and Hanoff (2021). What is worrying is the fact that, lots of schools yet no adopted systems of management more integrative, what promote the training integral of the students.

Chiavenato (2014) highlights in an entity, individuals represent the primary resource and, depending on how they are treated, they can decrease or expand on an organization's strengths and weaknesses. Furthermore, the author highlights what any enterprise productive only reaches success when involves the collaboration of several interconnected agents, each contributing their own resources.

It is essential that the manager knows himself and the group he leads so that work is carried out with maximum involvement of everyone. The attitudes of the leader in their day-to-day life with their team directly influences the attitudes of led and determine as to the relations interpersonal happen in the school. The way the manager manages the team determines the path followed by the group and, consequently, the results achieved by the school. When to the people participate from the creation of the standards and of the actions established for the group, they are in total harmony with the institution and contribute more effectively to a good result. (Gregório, 2005, p. 277-278).

The author highlights the importance of self-knowledge for the school manager and understanding

of group what leads, highlighting what to the attitudes of leader influence of form direct us led and mold to the relations interpersonal in the school. Emphasizes what and necessary the participation of the employees in the creation of actions and standards, arguing what the involvement of the people contributes to good results and he takes to their alignment with the institution. It also makes it clear that, through the self-knowledge, participatory and positive attitudes, can create an environment of work productive and harmonious, essential to the success.

The data points to the need for school management that is in tune with technological and social transformations. Management must be aligned with to the needs of environment educational, searching strategies what promote the training integral of the students. The lack of one management school effective he can compromise the quality of teaching, affect the reputation from the school before the society and the training of students in a short space of time. The search for strategies that promote the training integral of the students and of particular relevance node current context.

According to Sousa (2020), the need for management became evident school adjusted to social transformations. In this sense, it is responsible for review of planning and implementation of new projects, supervision of investments in innovation at school and restructuring of educational processes. That he can to have both impacts negatives as positives in the education, then processes bad evaluated and bad structured they can to generate problems node environment school.

It is necessary to reinvent education, analyze the contributions, risks and changes arising from interaction with digital culture, from the integration of TDIC, from resources, interfaces and media languages to practice pedagogical, explore the potential for integration between professional spaces, cultural and educational to the creation of contexts authentic of learning mediated by the technologies. To boost the student engagement in teaching and learning processes is pressing recontextualize to the methodologies of teaching ahead of the your social practices inherent to digital culture, that is, integrating media and TDIC in the development and recreation of active methodologies (Bacich and Moran, 2018, p.16-17).

The author states that there is a need to recreate education, considering the influence of digital

culture and the integration of digital technologies in practice pedagogical. AND fundamental explore the integration between spaces professionals, educational and cultural to create authentic mediated learning environments by the technologies. THE more worrying is what the lack of adaptation of the methodologies of teaching the culture digital he can consequently limit the involvement of the students. It is no exaggeration to say that driven by the constant need for integration of digital media and technologies, there has been a significant change in educational dynamics. Like this, concerns the gap between education and digital reality of students, as there is no way to disregard the strong connection of culture digital with the life everyday of the young people.

THE intersection between technology and education he has been one reality there is quite time, contributing both to improving student performance in teaching-learning process and for improving school management. Being like this:

Technology and education have been going hand in hand for some time now, whether for support and to improve the performance of the students node process of teaching and learning or to improve the management school. The process of digital transformation of schools has been happening at the same pace and with the resources that each school has, however it was accelerated by the pandemic Covid-19, when from one day to the next it forced schools to change management processes and implement new teaching methodologies with resource the technologies, bringing with you one set of challenges and opportunities for the schools (Paiva, 2021, p.43).

Sousa (2020) highlights the importance of adjustments in the administration school ahead of the changes in the school, being able to result in effects both negatives as positive in education. Bacich and Moran (2018) highlight the relevance of reinventing education, incorporating digital technologies into teaching practice to increase of student involvement. The interaction between education and technology has advanced, driven by the Covid-19 pandemic, accelerating the transition from the digital world in schools. This scenario brings opportunities and challenges, highlighting the need of if adapt to the requirements of this culture digital to creation of environments genuine of apprenticeship mediated by technologies (Paiva, 2021).

For De Almeida et al. (2007, p. 721) “the paradigm

shifts that come occurring in the educational field in recent times have been asking the school for a renewal of the school management model". In this context, the integration of new technologies, such as artificial intelligence and other online learning tools, become fundamental to enrich educational experiences. The use strategic teaching platforms, educational applications and data analysis can provide valuable insights into improving academic performance, enabling one approach more custom both to the teaching as to learning.

To the transformations node scope educational they are demanding one restructuring of model of management school traditional. THE integration of new technologies, enable the optimization of school management with enrichment of experiences educational. This form, the adaptation to the demands technological appears as one element essential to the continuous evolution of environment educational, aiming promote one education more efficient and inclusive with the service of the needs in constant transformation of the students.

METHODOLOGY

This study he was accomplished put quite of one revision bibliographical, with the analysis of scientific studies, articles and books on the importance of school management in the adaptation to the changes.

Through from the search bibliographical the researcher he does the survey of information what be relevant in the construction from the search scientific. This form, in one search scientific, the search bibliographical is important in gathering relevant information that contribute to the development of research, in the preparation of theme and in the revision bibliographical or frame theoretical (Of Sousa and al.,2021, p. 68)

THE strategy of search he was suitable, considering to the bases of data used and you following terms: management school, changes social and changes technological.

After selecting the articles, the most relevant data were read and extracted. relevant, including main arguments, limitations, abstracts, considerations ethics and synthesis of the results.

All the process of use and selection of sources he was driven following principles ethical, ensuring the

proper referencing of the information used and the proper quote of the authors.

PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

THE management school plays one paper fundamental in the adaptation of the schools to social and technological changes, as emphasized by Roldão and Hanoff (2021), what highlight the need of adoption of systems of management more efficient to meet these social demands. De Almeida et al. (2019) also highlight this importance by relating it to the needs of students and society to search for strategies to meet educational demands and promote training more integral of the students.

THE participation of the people in the actions established to the set and also in the creation of standards, contributes effectively to a good result, as mentioned by Gregório (2005). The collaboration of various agents in management school is fundamental to the success of the school institution, as highlighted by Gregory (2005).

The integration of digital technologies into pedagogical practice is fundamental in days current, as pointed put Sousa (2021), what highlights the need of explore the integration between professional, cultural, digital, educational spaces for creation of authentic environments of learning mediated by technologies.

CONCLUSION

The analysis carried out through this qualitative bibliographic review highlights the importance crucial from the management school in the capacity of the schools of if adapt to the both social and technological changes. The importance of management was highlighted school to be aligned with the needs of the educational environment, seeking strategies that promote the comprehensive education of students, who understand the interconnection between the management, society and technology.

The results obtained reinforce the need to initially adopt systems more efficient management systems to meet the educational demands of society contemporary. The lack of capable school management can compromise the quality of teaching and the training of the students, affecting the reputation from the school before society. Therefore, the active participation of managers, the understanding of the group who lead, self-knowledge,

and employee collaboration in creating standards and actions are essential elements for the success from the management in the school.

The present revision bibliographical contributes significantly to the quite academic to the consolidate and synthesize to the main approaches on the importance from the school management in adapting to changes, presenting a critical analysis of the sources used and highlighting interconnection of the concepts covered.

The results obtained reinforce the importance of school management as a process of social transformation, capable of driving schools towards change significant.

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